

Oxidation Behavior Modeling of Ceramic Coated Carbon/Carbon Composites

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SUMMARY: An analytical model to predict an oxidation rate of SiC-coated C/C composites is proposed and then the analytical predictions are compared with experimental observations. The oxidation of ceramic-coated C/C composites ordinary proceeds by oxygen diffusion through coating cracks. The coating cracks appear due to thermal expansion mismatch between the substrate C/C composite and the coating during the cooling process from coating treatment temperature to room temperature. Hence the present model simulates 1) Oxygen diffusion through coating cracks for calculation of an oxidation rate, and 2) Density of the coating cracks and crack opening. The analytically predicted oxidation rates are shown to be in good agreement with experimental ones in the various oxidation conditions.

KEYWORDS: SiC coating, C/C composites, Coating crack, Oxidation behavior

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix (C/C) composites are unique material possessing exceptional high heat resistance along with low density, high stiffness, and high strength. However, due to the serious shortcoming, i.e., easily oxidized to evaporate under high temperature environment, their applications have restricted to non-mechanical usage [1]. The oxidation of C/C composites begins from the temperature as low as about 773K [2]. In order to overcome this serious shortcoming for high temperature applications, various ceramic coatings on the surface of C/C composites have been currently studied for improvement oxidation resistance [3]. However, it is well known that a significant mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficient between the C/C substrate and a ceramic coating causes a number of coating cracks during the cooling process from the coating treatment to room temperature[4]. These cracks allow the oxygen diffusion toward the C/C substrate and this diffusion degrades the C/C substrate [5].

In this paper, an analytical model is proposed for the prediction of the weight loss due to oxidation of the SiC-coated C/C composites using information of coating cracks, such as crack spacing and crack width. To make the model self-consistent, an FEM model for the

prediction of crack spacing and crack width was also proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The C/C composites used in this study were fabricated by a processing route called "Preformed Yarn Method" [7]. The reinforcing fiber, fiber volume fraction, stacking sequence, and heat treatment temperature of this composite are Toray M40, 50%, UD or 0°/90°, and 2273K, respectively. The SiC coating on the surface of C/C composites was composed of 2 layers, i.e., a thin SiC conversion layer (about 3 μ m) and a thick and dense CVD coating layer (about 65 μ m). The CVD layer was thermally deposited at 1473K to 2073K and the conversion layer was formed by the direct chemical reaction of SiCl₄ with the near surface carbon in the substrate C/C composite.

Oxidation Tests

Oxidation tests have been carried out under xenon lamp heating and natural convection of atmosphere. In this apparatus, weight change under a constant temperature field was continuously measured and the temperature was monitored by an infrared thermo-viewer. The specimens were coated at 2073K and formed into the shape of 30mm x 30mm x 3mm^t.

OXIDATION BEHAVIOR

Characterization of SiC Coating Cracks

Fig.1 Cracks appeared on the top (a) and side (b) surfaces of SiC coating on the C/C composite.

Typical top and side views of the SiC coating of a 4mm x 4mm x 3mm^t specimen are shown in **Fig.1 (a)** and **(b)**, respectively. A lot of cracks shown in this figure were formed in the cooling process from the CVD temperature to room temperature due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the SiC coating and the C/C substrate. As shown in **Fig.1 (a)**, a fewer

number of wide cracks were observed on the top surface along the carbon fibers just under the SiC coating (0° cracks) and a larger number of narrow cracks (90° cracks) were observed perpendicular to the fibers. It should be noted that the transverse cracks, TCs, were frequently observed just under 0° cracks and thus the 0° cracks were affected profoundly by the TCs. The crack width distribution is actually different by the direction of the cross section as shown in **Fig.2 (a) and (b)**. On the side surface, coating cracks exist only in the

Fig.2 Distribution in opening width of cracks run parallel, 0° , and perpendicular, 90° , to the fiber direction in the outermost layer of the cross-ply C/C composite.

thickness direction of the specimen. This is because the thermal expansion coefficient in the out of plane direction of the C/C substrate is much larger than that of SiC.

The temperature dependence of crack opening was measured by use of a laser microscope attaching a high temperature furnace. This *in-situ* observation revealed that crack opening width becomes narrower linearly with temperature and tends to be zero at the coating temperature.

Oxidation Behavior of SiC-coated C/C Composites

The oxidation rate of the SiC-coated C/C composites is shown in **Fig.3**. It is follows from this figure that the SiC coating can lower the oxidation rate provided temperature being lower than 1973K. As is well known, oxidation behavior of the SiC-coated C/C composites can be classified into three regimes depending on the oxidation temperature and partial pressure of oxygen range. In the 1 atm environment following three regimes can be also observed clearly

(1) Chemical reaction controlling regime (CRR) below 1173K; excess amount of oxygen compared with the oxidation reaction rate is supplied from its environment.

(2) Diffusion controlling regime (BDR) between 1173K to 1973K; the oxidation reaction rate surpasses the oxygen diffusion.

(3) Active oxidation regime above 1973K; SiC oxidates to evaporate by the form of SiO + CO.

Fig.3 The Arrhenius plot of the oxidation rate of the bare and SiC coated C/C composites and predicted values in the diffusion controlling regime of SiC coated C/C composites.

ANALYTICAL MODELS

Oxidation Rate

In the temperature range between 1173K to 1973K and at 1 atm of environmental pressure, the oxidation rate of the SiC-coated C/C composites was controlled by the oxygen diffusion through the coating cracks. Let us consider the oxygen diffusion rate in this regime under the following assumptions.

- (1) Weight loss of the C/C substrate is far larger than the weight gain by silica grows.
- (2) All of oxygen diffuse through the coating crack is consumed by the C/C substrate.
- (3) Partial pressure of oxygen, P_{O_2} , at the top and bottom of coating cracks are equal to in atmospheric air and zero.

The oxygen diffusion rate, J_i , through a representative coating crack is given by;

$$J_c = D_{ci} \frac{\Delta C}{d} \quad (1),$$

where D_{ci} is an effective diffusion coefficient of oxygen, C is the concentration difference of oxygen across the coating crack, and d is the diffusion distance corresponding to the coating thickness. D_{ci} is given by eq. (2)[3]

$$\frac{1}{D_{ci}} = \frac{1}{D_b} + \frac{1}{D_{ki}} \quad (2),$$

where D_b is a molecular diffusion coefficient and D_{ki} is a Knudsen diffusion coefficient for one certain coating crack. D_b and D_{ki} are given by eqs. (3) and (4), respectively [10,17]

$$D_{ki} = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{8RT}{p M_{O_2}} \right)^{0.5} W_i \quad (3)$$

$$D_b = 5.9529 \times 10^{-24} \frac{\sqrt{T^3 \left(\frac{1}{M_{Air_{or}O_2}} + \frac{1}{M_{CO}} \right)}}{P \sigma_{Air_{or}O_2, CO}^2 \Omega_{Air_{or}O_2, CO}} \quad (4)$$

where R , W_i , T , P , M , σ , Ω , and ρ , in eqs.(2) and (3) are the gas constant, crack width, oxidation temperature, total pressure, the molar mass of the gaseous species, the collision diameter, the collision integral[11], and density, respectively. The crack opening width can be assumed to be linear function of absolute temperature and vanishes at coating temperature.

$$W_i(T) = \left(1 - \frac{T - 293.15}{2073.15 - 293.15} \right) W_i(R.T.) \quad (5),$$

where $W_i(R.T.)$ is a crack width at room temperature. In the actual specimen, there are a large number of coating cracks with various crack widths. Hence, the total oxygen diffusion rate, J_{total} , is given using width probability, λ_i , and fractional area of coating cracks, f_c by

$$J_{total} = f_c \times \sum \left(\lambda_i \frac{D_{ci}}{d} \frac{PM_{O_2}}{RT} \right) \quad (6)$$

where P is P_{O_2} on the surface of the coating and the summation is taken over W_i in the length l of the coating. The outward diffusion of carbon oxides prevents the inward diffusion of oxygen. This contribution can be expressed by χ in eq. (8). Then, the oxidation rate of the SiC-coated C/C composites, dW/dt , is given by

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = \frac{24}{32} \frac{f_c}{\chi} \times \sum \left(\lambda_i \frac{D_{ci}}{\delta} \frac{PM_{O_2}}{RT} \right) \quad (7).$$

$$\chi = \frac{-\chi_{top}}{\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 + \chi_{top}} \right)} \quad (8)$$

here χ_{top} is molar fraction of oxygen on the surface of the coating.

Coating Cracking

In order to analyze SiC coating cracking, we paid attention to the in-plane thermal tensile stress, σ_x , appeared near the interface because the maximum stress, $\sigma_{x \max}$, always predicted to be induced near the interface. According to microscopic observation, coating cracks frequently extended into the C/C substrate and these cracks were considered to have strong influence to the stress distribution in the coating. Hence in the analysis, coating cracks accompanying the substrate cracks were introduced.

Fig.4 shows the distribution of computed in-plane thermal stresses near the interface of the coating for coating thickness 80 μ m and substrate cracking depth 12.6 μ m (experimentally obtained averaged value). In this analysis, it was assumed that specimen length was 5mm, and the origin of the coordinate was at the center of the specimen. When no crack was introduced, σ_x was given in curve (a) and $\sigma_{x \max}$, appears at the origin. Hence the first crack was introduced at the center of the specimen. The σ_x just after the first cracking is shown by curve (b), on which $\sigma_{x \max}$ appears at a distance of 137 μ m from the first crack. The σ_x distribution in the thickness direction revealed that σ_x changes linearly and the maximum and minimum tensile stresses appear on the interface and the top surface, respectively. Thus,

Figure 4 Distribution of σ_x derived from the FEM analysis.

this rather sharp peak in curve should be induced by the bending deformation of the coating. It follows from this figure that the second crack should appear at this peak and by the same token the sequential cracks, , , and so on, are also expected to occur near the

Figure 5 Dependence of $\sigma_{x \max}$ location on the substrate cracking depth.

each previous crack. Thus in this maximum stress model, cracking of the SiC coating is suggested to proceed from the center to the edge of the specimen by almost same interval. The location of $\sigma_{x \max}$ from the adjacent crack depends on the substrate cracking depth as shown in **Fig.5**. It can be seen in this figure that the $\sigma_{x \max}$ location becomes shorter than the coating thickness, when the substrate cracking depth becomes shorter than $6\mu\text{m}$. However, in the actual specimens, no such crack spacing was observed in spite of varying the substrate cracking depth from 0 to several tens μm .

CONFIRMATION OF PREDICTIONS

Oxidation Rate

The oxidation rate calculated in the BDR by eq. (8), solid and dotted lines, was compared with that obtained in the oxidation tests in **Fig.3**. It follows from this figure that the calculated results reasonably well agreed with experimental values. The weight loss rate was decreased with oxidation time due to formation of the silica growth and resulting decrease of crack opening width. The predicted values in Fig. 3 were based on the initial slope of weight loss vs. time curves. This time dependent behavior can be also predictable by use of the silica growth rate reported by Filipuzzi [19] and calculating the crack width change during the oxidation tests [6].

Crack Spacing and Crack Opening

Figure 6 Dependence of σ_x^c on the crack spacing derived from the FEM analysis.

Fig.6 shows the stress at the midsection interface of adjacent, σ_x^c , as a function of cracked segment length, crack spacing. The tensile fracture stress of the SiC coating should be lower than the stress when crack spacing is twice of the saturated crack spacing and higher than the stress obtained when crack spacing is the saturated one. From these condition we can estimate the tensile fracture strength of the present CVD-SiC coating as shown in the shaded region. Thus assuming the tensile strength is 950MPa, we predicted the maximum crack spacing, l_{max} , and the minimum crack spacing, l_{min} , from the condition that l_{min} is one half of the l_{max} as shown in **Fig.7**. In this figure the measured mean crack spacing is also plotted. Comparison of the predicted crack spacing with the measured one lead to the conclusion that the σ_x^c condition is adequate.

Fig. 7 Comparison of the predicted crack spacing with those of the experimental observations.

Finally the averaged crack width computed from the FEM calculus is compared with the measured one in **Fig.9**. The predicted crack width has a tendency to become wider as coating thickness increases and this tendency is reasonably agree with the experimental observation.

Fig. 9 Comparison of the predicted crack width with those of the experimental observations.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The oxidation rate of the SiC-coated C/C composites in the diffusion control regime can be reasonably well predicted by use of the present diffusion model.
- 2) Coating cracks propagate not only in the SiC coating but also into the C/C substrate.
- 3) Cracking of the SiC coating can be explained by the maximum stress.

- 4) By combining the proposed two models for oxidation rate and coating cracking, we can predict self-consistently oxidation behavior of ceramic coated C/C composites.

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